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REVIEW PAPER

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AN EVALUATION ON THE APPLICATIONS OF SOME MARINE BIOPOLYMERS

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Abstract

The environmental pollution caused by plastic waste is increasingly becoming a significant concern. As a result, the use of biodegradable plastics is gaining more importance. This study provides a detailed review of the applications of marine-sourced biodegradable plastics based on chitosan, gelatin, and alginate. Chitosan, a polysaccharide found in the shells of crustaceans, possesses properties that allow it to biologically degrade without harming the environment. These biodegradable characteristics make chitosan an eco-friendly alternative to traditional plastics. Chitosan is used in various fields such as food packaging, drug delivery systems, and wound healing materials. Gelatin is a protein derivative obtained from animal bones and skins. This material also possesses properties that allow it to biodegrade without harming the environment. Gelatin flexible nature makes it suitable for various applications in the plastic industry. It is used in areas such as food packaging, pharmaceutical capsules, and phototherapy devices. Alginate, derived from seaweed, is another polysaccharide that is biodegradable and environmentally friendly. Its high water-absorption capacity makes it an ideal material for applications such as food packaging and drug delivery systems. Marine-sourced chitosan, gelatin, and alginate-based biodegradable plastics stand out as eco-friendly plastic alternatives. The use of these materials can help reduce the environmental damage caused by plastic waste and contribute to a sustainable future. However, further research and development are needed on the industrial-scale use and recycling of these materials. In conclusion, marine-sourced biodegradable plastics have various applications and hold significant potential as environmentally friendly plastic alternatives. More efforts should be made in the future to increase the use of these materials and reduce plastic waste.

Keywords: Marine Biopolymers, chitosan, gelatin, alginate

Introduction

The environmental impacts of plastics are an undeniable reality. Due to the difficulty of recycling plastics, they cause significant pollution in both marine and terrestrial environments. Therefore, efforts are being made to reduce the environmental impact of plastics through recycling and the use of alternative materials (Tennakoon et al., 2023). It is well-known that the materials used in commercial food packaging are predominantly petroleum-based plastics. Materials such as polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE), and polystyrene (PS) are synthetic polymers derived from fossil fuels like petroleum. These plastics are preferred for food packaging due to their flexibility, durability, and cost-effectiveness (Fu and Dudley, 2021; Dharini et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2023). The production and consumption of plastic packaging bags are enormous, and their environmental impacts are creating serious problems. The annual production of 500 billion plastic bags and a consumption rate of one million per minute demonstrate the unsustainable dimensions of plastic use. These production and consumption rates result in the intense consumption of natural resources and the generation of large amounts of waste. Food packaging films make up 40% of plastic waste, further increasing the environmental burden of these products. Because plastics take a very long time to decompose in nature, the waste discarded into the environment after use can cause permanent damage to ecosystems (Macena et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2023). However, since most of these plastics are single-use, they can pose significant challenges in terms of environmental sustainability and waste management. The high usage of disposable plastics, their return to the environment as waste, and their prolonged decomposition times can have adverse effects on ecological balance. This creates a cycle of continuous environmental degradation, necessitating urgent measures to address the issue through enhanced recycling programs and the development of more sustainable, biodegradable alternatives (Kibria et al., 2023). Particularly, the impact on water resources and marine life is severe. Plastics accumulate on the surface of the water, threatening the habitats of marine creatures. In some cases, this can lead to wildlife mistaking plastic debris for food and consuming it. This not only poses a direct threat to marine organisms through ingestion but also disrupts the entire marine ecosystem, affecting the health and survival of these species. This situation can harm the health of marine life and also pose risks to humans through bioaccumulation. (Thushari & Senevirathna, 2020; Yu & Singh, 2023; Rahman et al., 2023; Ghosh et al., 2023). This type of plastic consumption and waste management model is leading to a global environmental crisis, and overcoming this crisis requires measures such as the use of alternative materials, the development of reusable and recyclable packaging solutions, and changes in consumer behavior (Rhodes, 2018; Pilapitiya & Ratnayake, 2024). This situation is increasing interest in alternative packaging materials and the search for environmentally friendly packaging solutions. In this study, a detailed review has been conducted on the applications of biodegradable plastics based on marine-derived chitosan, gelatin, and alginate. These polymeric materials stand out as environmentally friendly plastic alternatives due to their biodegradable and non-harmful properties to the environment. Chitosan is a natural polysaccharide found in the shells of marine crustaceans (Shahidi et al., 1999; Rinaudo, 2006; Younes & Rinaudo, 2015; Santos et al., 2020). This material is used in many different industries due to its antimicrobial properties and high mechanical strength (Ke et al., 2021; Mawazi et al., 2024). Thanks to its biodegradable nature, chitosan helps reduce plastic waste and offers a more sustainable alternative to environmentally harmful plastics (Wrońska et al., 2023). Gelatin, derived from animal bones and skins, is a protein-based material (Rather et al., 2022; Garcia Londoño et al., 2023). Due to its flexibility and water absorption properties, it is used in areas such as food packaging and pharmaceutical coatings (Hanani et al., 2014; Riahi et al., 2023). The biodegradable nature of gelatin contributes to reducing plastic waste and facilitating recycling processes. Alginate is a natural

polysaccharide derived from seaweed (Abka-Khajouei et al., 2022; Bi et al., 2022). This material is used in the food industry as a mold former and stabilizer due to its gel-forming properties (Qin et al., 2018; Raus et al., 2021). The biodegradable nature of alginate helps reduce plastic waste and offers a more environmentally friendly alternative to harmful materials. The biodegradable nature of alginate contributes to reducing plastic waste and offers a more environmentally friendly alternative to materials that harm the environment. Applications of biodegradable plastics based on marine-derived chitosan, gelatin, and alginate hold a significant place in the fields of environmental sustainability and green technology. These materials enable the reduction of plastic waste and the replacement of environmentally harmful materials with more eco-friendly options, thus contributing to leaving a cleaner environment for future generations. In conclusion, the applications of biodegradable plastics based on marine-derived chitosan, gelatin, and alginate possess significant potential in the fields of environmental sustainability and green technology. Wider use and preference of these materials in industrial applications will contribute significantly to adopting an environmentally sensitive approach and reducing plastic waste.

Gelatin, Chitosan and Alginate Applications

Today, environmental pollution, the damage caused by plastic waste to nature, and sustainability issues are increasingly gaining importance. Plastic is a material commonly used in modern industrial processes and plays a vital role in many sectors (Rodrigues et al., 2019; Kassab et al., 2023). From the packaging industry to the automotive sector, and from electronic goods to medical devices, the use of plastic materials is widespread in numerous fields (Vieyra et al., 2022; Kong et al., 2023). However, these large quantities of plastic production also bring various environmental and social issues. Particularly, the widespread use of single-use plastics is exacerbating environmental pollution and threatening natural life. Plastics accumulating in seas and on land damage ecosystems and negatively affect wildlife (Thushari & Senevirathna, 2020). Additionally, the extraction and processing of raw materials used in plastic production contribute to the depletion of natural resources and the degradation of ecosystems. Therefore, the use of biodegradable polymeric materials is garnering significant interest as environmentally friendly alternatives to plastics. Biodegradable polymeric materials such as chitosan, gelatin, and alginate stand out due to their biodegradable properties and non-harmful impact on the environment. Chitosan is a polymer derived from chitin, which is a natural polysaccharide precursor found in the external skeletons of marine crustaceans (Jiménez-Gómez & Cecilia, 2020). Chitin is transformed into chitosan through chemical processes. Chitosan possesses several advantages, including antimicrobial properties, biodegradability, and being ecofriendly (Hameed et al., 2022). Due to these characteristics, chitosan is used in various fields including food packaging, drug delivery systems, and tissue engineering. Gelatin is a protein polymer derived from animal bones, skin, and connective tissue. Its biodegradable nature and lack of environmental harm make it a significant option among environmentally friendly plastic alternatives. Gelatin is used in the food industry as a coating and packaging material, in the pharmaceutical industry as a capsule material, and in the photographic industry for film production (Rather et al., 2022; Garcia Londoño et al., 2023; Hanani et al., 2014; Riahi et al., 2023). Alginate is a natural polymer derived from seaweed. Its biodegradability, non-toxicity to the environment, and gel-forming capabilities make it widely used in various industries. In the food industry, alginate serves as a gelling and thickening agent, while in the pharmaceutical industry, it is utilized in drug delivery systems, and in tissue engineering. Alginate holds a significant position among environmentally friendly plastic alternatives (Abka-Khajouei et al., 2022; Bi et al., 2022; Qin et al., 2018; Raus et al., 2021). The use of biodegradable polymeric materials contributes to reducing plastic waste and minimizing environmental damage. The non-

harmful nature of these materials, their ability to biodegrade, and their recyclability represent significant steps toward a sustainable future. Increasing the use of biodegradable polymeric materials like chitosan, gelatin, and alginate across various industries will substantially aid in adopting environmentally friendly plastic alternatives and reducing plastic waste. Therefore, promoting and expanding the use of biodegradable polymeric materials will play a crucial role in building an eco-friendly future. Li et al. (2022a) conducted a study focused on the development of edible gelatin films modified with pullulan, exploring their potential use in the production of edible spice packets. The study presents a significant innovation in edible film technology by developing composite films that incorporate pullulan, gelatin, and sodium alginate. The research investigates the film formation mechanism and resistance to grease oxidation of films composed of these three materials through practical application.

In the study by Li et al. (2022a), Figures 1 and 2 provide illustrations of the film production process and the resulting films, respectively. Figures 1 and 2 were used in this study because this study is open access. It has been suggested that when used in conjunction with sodium alginate, pullulan can improve the physicochemical properties of gelatin films. Pullulan, a natural polysaccharide, was utilized in this study to form a polyelectrolyte complex. This combination is indicative of the potential to improve film integrity and functionality, leveraging the unique properties of each component for enhanced performance in edible film applications. In the study, the weak alkaline environment created by sodium tripolyphosphate makes gelatin negatively charged, while pullulan remains un-charged in this setting. Due to these electrostatic interactions, pullulan combines with gelatin to form a film layer. To understand the interaction between these components, methods such as Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) and microstructural observations have been used in the research. These techniques help elucidate the molecular interactions and structural formation crucial for developing effective biodegradable films. These methods provide information about the chemical bonds and structural arrangements between the materials. The mechanical properties of the film material, such as tensile strength and elongation at break, have been measured through tests that evaluate the film's durability and flexibility. Regarding the functionality of the film, its capacity to prevent the oxidation of oils is of critical importance; therefore, its oxygen permeability and light barrier properties have also been measured. Oxygen and light are factors that can accelerate the oxidation process of oils, so minimizing these properties extends the product's shelf life. Additionally, solubility tests in water were conducted to assess the film's practical usability, determining how it will behave during the consumption of the product it is used with. The thermal stability and color properties were analyzed using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), which indicates the film's resistance to temperature changes and its aesthetic qualities. The oxidation resistance was also measured, serving as an important indicator of the film's protective properties. Under weak alkaline conditions provided by sodium tripolyphosphate, electrostatic repulsion has been observed between negatively charged gelatin molecules and polyanionic sodium alginate. This scenario has facilitated the formation of hydrogen bonds by pullulan among these molecules, allowing for cross-linking. This cross-linking is a critical factor that significantly influences the structure and functionality of the film. The study has found that the ratio of pullulan to gelatin plays a decisive role in the properties of the film. When used in a 1:1 ratio with gelatin, the films exhibit the best mechanical strength, oxygen barrier properties, thermodynamic stability, protection against UV rays, and the best fibrous microstructure. This ratio has also maximized the film's antioxidant properties and delayed the oxidation of fats. However, inappropriate amounts of pullulan can show pro-oxidative effects, which could accelerate the oxidation process. Furthermore, the study reveals that the film's water solubility is not significantly different from that of hydrophilic materials, an important feature for films

that come into direct contact with food. Additionally, the film's hydrogen bond structure can be further enriched with antioxidant substances, thereby enhancing the film's resistance to oxidative stress. Consequently, this research offers new and effective solutions for the design of edible internal packaging. However, before being used as a material that comes into contact with food, the safety and antimicrobial properties of such films need to be further optimized. This type of innovation holds great potential for sustainability and environmental sensitivity in food preservation technologies (Li et al., 2022a).

Figure 1. The visual images of sodium alginate–gelatin-based films (Pul: Pullulan, Gel: Gelatin, Sa: Sodium alginate) (Li et. al., 2022a)

Figure 2. Images of film samples in the study (Li et. al., 2022a)

Xu et al. (2015) conducted research on the chemical interactions between citric acid (CA) and proteins. As mentioned in the related study, the reaction between citric acid (CA) and proteins proceeds through two main fundamental steps, as described below (Xu et al., 2015).

1. **Nucleophilic Substitution Reaction:** A nucleophilic substitution reaction occurs between one or more carboxyl groups (-COOH) in citric acid (CA) and the amino group (-NH₂) in a protein molecule. This type of reaction is characterized by a

nucleophile (in this case, the amino group in the protein) attacking an electron-rich atom in a substrate (in this case, the carboxyl group in CA). As a result of this reaction, new chemical bonds are formed, and significant changes typically occur in the molecular structure.

- Intramolecular and Intermolecular Cross-linking (CLG):** Due to CA molecules containing multiple carboxyl groups, a single CA molecule can react with multiple protein molecules. This leads to both intramolecular (within a single protein molecule) and intermolecular (between different protein molecules) cross-linking (CLG). Cross-linking can significantly alter the physical and chemical properties of proteins, increase their structural integrity, and broaden their applicability in various applications (Xu et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2023). Especially in fields such as biomedical engineering, tissue engineering, and drug delivery systems, these types of chemical modifications and cross-linking are strategically used to improve the functionality of materials. For instance, proteins modified by these methods can be used to create more robust wound dressings or more effective drug delivery systems. Such cross-linked proteins may be more stable in biological environments and can provide sustained therapeutic effects.

Fish gelatin, derived from fish waste, is a protein source often used as an alternative to beef or pork gelatin. This type of gelatin is particularly favored for halal food products because beef or pork gelatin cannot be consumed by communities with dietary restrictions. Cross-linking studies in fish gelatin using citric acid (CA) have been researched by Uranga et al. (2016). Cross-linking (CLG) is a chemical modification process performed using multifunctional agents such as citric acid. This process aims to improve the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the material by creating chemical bonds between gelatin molecules. For example, enhancements can be made in mechanical strength, thermal stability, melting point, and biodegradability. Such research can make significant contributions to developing sustainable and acceptable food packaging materials or biomedical products. Additionally, it can provide guidance on optimizing cross-linking, under what conditions the best results can be achieved, and selecting the most suitable type of gelatin for potential applications (Uranga et al., 2016).

In the study conducted by Nataraj et al. (2018), chitosan was modified with citric acid. Chitosan is a natural polysaccharide derived from the shells of marine crustaceans and is often preferred due to its biocompatible, bio-renewable, and biodegradable properties. In this description, the protonation of chitosan in an acidic solution, meaning the addition of protons (hydrogen ions) by acid groups, has been performed. This process improves chitosan's ability to form stable structures beneficial for various applications including medical and environmental fields. This process is typically performed to enhance the solubility and processability of chitosan. Subsequently, chitosan molecules react with citric acid (CA) molecules at high temperatures, undergoing an amidation reaction (CLG reaction) through intramolecular chains or intermolecular chain ester bonds. Amidation typically involves the formation of an amide (and water) from the reaction of an acid and an amine. Here, an amide bond is formed between the amine group of chitosan and the carboxyl group of citric acid. This process alters the chemical structure and, consequently, the properties of chitosan, potentially enhancing its functionality for various applications. For example, improvements can be targeted in mechanical properties, the hydrophilic/hydrophobic balance, and biological interactions. Such modifications are carried out to broaden the use of chitosan in various fields, including medical applications, drug delivery systems, and wound dressings (Nataraj et al., 2018). These improvements help adapt chitosan functionalities to meet specific demands

in these applications, making it a highly versatile and valuable material in the biomedical field.

Yang et al. (2024) have illustrated the structure of a matrix obtained using citric acid as a cross-linker with components chitosan and gelatin. The research indicates that CA-cross-linked chitosan/gelatin hydrogels can be used effectively for the release of a hydrophobic molecule, curcumin (Cur), in simulated intestinal fluid. The effects of CA and Cur on the hydrogels shed light on the potential biomedical applications of these hydrogels. This highlights the utility of such hydrogels in targeting and controlled release systems, potentially improving the efficacy of therapeutic interventions. It has been noted that the hydrogels have provided effective drug release within 100 minutes at a 40% release rate. This suggests that hydrogels can advance therapeutic efficacy by ensuring that the medication reaches the targeted area. Such systems are particularly useful in treating intestinal diseases because the drug can be released directly in the intestines where it is needed. Additionally, both curcumin (Cur) and citric acid (CA) have improved the physical and biological properties of the hydrogels. Observed improvements in tensile strength, antioxidant activity, and antibacterial activity indicate that the hydrogels have become more durable and beneficial. This improvement of properties underscores the potential of these hydrogels as effective carriers in drug delivery systems, particularly in environments where targeted action and biocompatibility are critical. These properties support the use of hydrogels in various biomedical applications. It has been noted that the CGA0.4 sample rapidly swells in deionized water, reaching a maximum swelling index of 539 g/g within 40 minutes, indicating that this material can effectively absorb water and that this feature can be optimized for drug release. Additionally, the CGA0.4Cur sample has been shown to degrade by more than 90% in a combined solution after seven days, suggesting that this hydrogel is rapidly biodegradable and may have a low environmental impact. This quick degradation rate not only minimizes long-term environmental risks but also indicates the potential for these hydrogels to deliver therapeutic agents effectively within a short timeframe, enhancing their utility in applications requiring timely biodegradation. In conclusion, this study demonstrates that CA-cross-linked chitosan/gelatin hydrogels provide a theoretical foundation for their use in drug delivery systems specifically designed for the treatment of intestinal diseases. The enhanced properties of these hydrogels, such as bio-accessibility, mechanical strength, and biological activity, potentially make them valuable and effective therapeutic tools (Yang et al., 2024). These improvements suggest that the hydrogels could be critically important in targeted medical applications, offering precise and controlled drug release capabilities that could revolutionize treatment methodologies for gastrointestinal conditions.

Li et al. (2022b) investigated the effects of varying concentrations of gelatin (GL) and sodium alginate (SA) on the mechanical properties of films. Additionally, to improve the antibacterial properties of the composite film, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) were incorporated to create a nanocomposite film (SA/GL/Ag film). The study also examined the effect of the SA/GL/Ag antibacterial composite film on fruit preservation, aiming to provide a reference for the development of an environmentally friendly antibacterial food packaging film (Li et al., 2022b). This study aims to offer potential environmentally friendly solutions for the food packaging industry. Understanding the effects of polymers like gelatin and sodium alginate on mechanical properties is crucial for optimizing the performance of these materials in food preservation. Notably, the incorporation of silver nanoparticles in the creation of a nanocomposite film highlights its potential to extend the shelf life of fruits and its antibacterial properties. Innovations like these can advance food safety and reduce food waste, thereby minimizing environmental impact. This research represents a significant step

towards developing sustainable and effective solutions in food packaging technologies. In summary, the SA/GL/Ag nanocomposite films have been prepared using sodium alginate and gelatin as film-forming substrates and silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) as an antibacterial agent. These films have been enhanced in terms of mechanical strength, thermal stability, and antibacterial activity. The addition of silver nanoparticles has improved the overall performance of the films, both strengthening their mechanical resistance and enhancing their thermal properties. Additionally, these films have demonstrated effective antibacterial activity against Gram-positive *S. aureus* and Gram-negative *E. coli* bacteria. The SA/GL/Ag coating application for mandarin preservation has extended the shelf life of the fruit by delaying spoilage and quality loss. After long-term storage, the amount of silver detected in the mandarins remained within safe limits, indicating that this coating is suitable for food safety. These findings demonstrate that the SA/GL/Ag film has wide potential uses in the field of food packaging and can offer an effective solution for extending the shelf life of food products. The applications of such nanotechnology have the potential to improve sustainability and efficiency in the food industry, as well as provide significant benefits in reducing food waste and protecting consumer health (Li et al., 2022b).

Elhadeif et al. (2024) investigated the effects of incorporating date pits extracts (DPE) into sodium alginate packaging films on the preservation of raw ground beef. The focus of the study is on evaluating date palm seed extract as a potential bioactive additive for food packaging, thanks to its antioxidant and antimicrobial properties. Initially, the research involved preparing films based on sodium alginate, into which date palm seed extract was mixed to create new bioactive films. These films were characterized in detail regarding their physical, optical, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties. This characterization is critically important for assessing the potential efficacy of the films in preserving raw meat. Subsequently, these bioactive films were applied to raw ground beef stored at 4°C for 14 days. Throughout this period, various parameters such as microbiological activity, oxidative stability, color changes, and sensory characteristics were observed. These observations are crucial for understanding the role of date palm seed extract in meat preservation. Additionally, chemometric analyses (PCA and heat maps) were conducted within the study to understand the relationships among all parameters during storage. These analyses advance the understanding of the connections and interactions between variables, thus identifying which factors play a more significant role in meat preservation. This approach allows for a more precise determination of how bioactive films contribute to maintaining the quality and safety of stored meat. The combination of DPE (date palm seed extract) with gelatin-sodium alginate films has been developed for the purpose of preserving food quality, and these films have been reported to surpass control films in terms of physical, optical, antioxidant, and antibacterial activities. This indicates that DPE's natural antioxidant and antimicrobial properties can function effectively within food packaging films. The research has demonstrated that these films extend the shelf life of packaged raw ground beef during storage at 4°C. It has been noted that a concentration of 1.5% DPE is the most effective method for maintaining the freshness of beef in refrigerator conditions for up to approximately 14 days. This application highlights DPE's potential as a valuable additive in food packaging solutions aimed at improving food preservation. This provides strong evidence of the value of using natural preservatives in the food industry. Additionally, the chemometric techniques employed have provided significant insights in the analyses linking oxidative and microbiological variables with sensory and instrumental color properties. These methods have enabled differentiation between various samples and improved interpretation of the data. Consequently, this study demonstrates that the combination of sodium alginate and date palm seed extract can be effective in maintaining the long-term freshness and quality of

raw ground beef. The antimicrobial and antioxidant properties of date palm seed extract indicate its potential to offer innovative and natural solutions in food packaging technologies (Elhadeef et al., 2024).

Chiaoprakobkij et al. (2019) conducted research on a new bio-composite film produced using environmentally friendly methods with materials derived from various biological sources. The study specifically focuses on the development and detailed examination of a new composite film designed for biomedical applications, known as BCAGG (comprising bacterial cellulose, alginate, gelatin, and glycerol). Each of the materials used in the films comes from a different biological origin and possesses unique properties, making them suitable for specialized applications in the biomedical field. This combination of components in the BCAGG films leverages their distinct characteristics, aiming to create films with advanced performance for medical use. Bacterial cellulose (BC) is known for its high strength and moisture retention capabilities; alginate, a natural polymer derived from seaweed, stands out for its film-forming and gel-forming capacities; and gelatin, a protein-based material sourced from animal cells, is crucial for biocompatibility. The combination of these materials aims to harness the benefits of each, creating a synergistic effect in areas such as mechanical properties, moisture resistance, and biocompatibility. Additionally, the study has taken a significant step in evaluating the produced film for biomedical applications. The film has been tested for cytotoxicity (potential to harm cells) and biocompatibility (compatibility with biological environments) through cell studies conducted on human keratinocytes (HaCat cells), providing valuable insights into its suitability for medical use. This comprehensive approach not only showcases the potential of the BCAGG films in the biomedical sector but also emphasizes the importance of thorough testing to ensure safety and effectiveness in clinical settings. These tests are of critical importance in determining the potential impacts of the film on human health. The study highlights that these composites are produced using a casting method, an environmentally friendly and cost-effective approach that does not use organic solvents. This method is a significant step towards sustainability and reducing negative impacts on the environment. The BCAGG films have been noted for displaying remarkable properties in terms of biocompatibility and physical performance. The flexibility demonstrated by the film, both in dry and wet conditions, indicates its potential to mimic the natural elastic properties of the skin in biomedical applications, particularly in treatments involving the skin. This attribute advances the utility of BCAGG films in the medical field, where adaptable and gentle solutions are crucial for patient care and recovery. Additionally, features such as water absorption capacity and oxygen permeability make the film suitable for applications like wound dressings. Experiments conducted on L929 and HaCat cell lines have shown that the BCAGG film promotes cell adhesion and proliferation. This significantly improves the film's usability in wound healing and tissue engineering applications. The film's ease of use with surgical tweezers and its resistance to being punctured by a stitching needle are notable. These properties provide practical and effective solutions for use in surgical environments. Consequently, the attributes offered by the BCAGG film make it a valuable material in the biomedical field, particularly in critical applications such as surgery and wound care. This integration of functionality and practicality underlines the potential of BCAGG films to advance medical treatments and patient outcomes. The results of the study demonstrate that these types of bio-composite films offer significant advantages both in terms of environmental sustainability and biomedical performance. These findings can serve as an important reference for future research and applications, potentially guiding further development in the creation and utilization of bio-composite materials. The insights gained from this research emphasize the potential of integrating eco-friendly materials with advanced

biomedical technologies, thereby promoting healthier ecosystems and improving medical outcomes.

Conclusion

Petroleum-based synthetic polymers are a popular choice in the food packaging industry due to their lightweight, flexibility, durability, and low cost. However, the environmental impacts of these materials are increasingly causing concern. Single-use plastic packaging can lead to environmentally harmful waste and pollution. Therefore, given the concerns about sustainability and environmental impacts, more research on alternative packaging materials is necessary. The rapid increase in global plastic production and consumption necessitates greater efforts to solve these issues. Developing more comprehensive strategies for sustainable plastic production and use, supporting innovative recycling technologies, and increasing public awareness will be crucial steps for the future of the plastic industry. Among alternative packaging materials, there are biodegradable polymers, as well as recyclable materials like paper and cardboard. Biodegradable polymers are made from natural resources and can decompose without harming the environment. These materials have the potential to replace plastic packaging and reduce environmental impacts. However, further research is needed regarding the cost and performance of biodegradable polymers to fully assess their viability as sustainable alternatives to traditional plastics. This exploration could lead to more environmentally friendly packaging solutions that do not compromise on quality or functionality. The use of marine-derived biodegradable polymers such as chitosan, gelatin, and alginate are seen as a significant development that increases interest in sustainable and environmentally friendly material technologies. This mini-review on the applications of these polymers aims to advance our understanding of their potential and how they can be utilized in various industries. This mini-review will attempt to broadly list the application areas of biodegradable polymers like chitosan, gelatin, and alginate.

- **Environmental Impact and Sustainability**

Marine-derived biodegradable polymers are emerging as environmentally friendly alternatives that can replace petroleum-based plastics. Chitosan, gelatin, and alginate, being derived from renewable sources and easily degradable in nature, have a less harmful impact on the ecosystem. The use of these polymers has the potential to reduce environmental pollution caused by single-use plastic products.

- **Biomedical Applications**

The biocompatibility, bioactivity, and biodegradability of these biopolymers make them valuable in the biomedical field, especially for applications such as drug delivery systems, tissue engineering scaffolds, wound dressings, and surgical sutures. For example, the antimicrobial properties of chitosan support wound healing, while the cell-friendly structure of gelatin is ideal for tissue engineering. Alginate is used in wound care products and drug delivery systems due to its high water-retention capacity.

- **Applications in the Food Industry**

In the field of food packaging, the water barrier properties and biodegradability of these polymers can help maintain food freshness while reducing environmental impact. Alginate and chitosan can also function as food preservatives; they extend the shelf life of food by preventing oxidation or inhibiting microbial growth. Gelatin, being a natural and edible film former, can be used as a coating material for meat and dairy products.

- **Water Treatment Processes**

The ability of chitosan to adsorb heavy metals and other pollutants has made it a valuable resource in water treatment applications. These biocompatible polymers offer an environmentally friendly method for purifying contaminated water and creating safer drinking water sources.

- **Agricultural Applications**

Bio-based polymers can also be used in agriculture as materials that support plant growth. For example, alginate used in seed coatings can improve the germination rate of seeds. Additionally, the protective properties of chitosan against plant diseases can be utilized to improve plant health and increase yield.

- **Advanced Research and Development**

Ongoing research and development are crucial for enhancing the functionality of these biopolymers and discovering new application areas. Particularly, the properties of composite materials derived from combinations of different biopolymers can be highly customizable and have their application possibilities expanded.

In conclusion, marine-derived biodegradable polymers such as chitosan, gelatin, and alginate offer a wide range of applications, holding significant potential both in terms of environmental sustainability and technological innovation. The future technological applications of these materials will be crucial steps in integrating environmental responsibility with innovation.

Ethical approval

Not applicable

Informed consent

Not available

Data availability statement

The authors declare that data can be provided by corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interests for publishing this study.

Contribution of authors

All authors of the study made contributions in various aspects of the research. They were involved in writing of the article. Each author likely had specific roles and responsibilities within these areas, but the exact details of their individual contributions are provided below.

Bayram Kızılkaya : Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing original draft

Dilek Şenol Bahçeci : Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Validation, Review and editing

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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